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“Druggability and Amino Acid Variability of the Catalytic Site of SARS-CoV-2 Nsp15 Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

Background:

The Non-structural protein 15 (nsp15) is an endoribonuclease which is a nidoviral RNA uridylylate-specific endoribonuclease (NendoU) with C-terminal catalytic activity. Nsp15 belongs to the EndoU family; and they carry an RNA endonuclease activity to produce 2'-3' cyclic phosphodiester and 5'-hydroxyl termini. ([kim et al., 2020](#))

SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 has 88% sequence identity (ID) with SARS-CoV-1 nsp15, 50% with Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) nsp15, and 43% with human coronavirus (H-CoV-229E) nsp15. ([Kim et al., 2020](#))

Mutant nsp15 of mouse hepatitis virus strain A59 (MHV-A59), a model coronavirus, which expressed an unstable catalysis-deficient nsp15 led to early protective immune response through induction of type I interferon and an early apoptotic cell death. The loss of nsp15 activity also led to shortening of the disease acute hepatitis in mice and loss of typical lesions associated with MHV-WT, highlighting its role in coronavirus pathogenesis. Inactive nsp15 caused stimulation of the host dsRNA sensors associated with an array of immune responses. ([Deng et al., 2017](#))

The SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 monomer structure consists of an N-terminal oligomerization domain, a middle-domain, and a C-terminal NendoU catalytic domain as shown in figure 1 taken from [Kim et al., 2020](#). The functionally active form of SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 is a hexamer same as the SARS- and MERS-CoV nsp15s. ([Kim et al., 2020](#))

Figure 1. Crystal structure of Nsp15 endoribonuclease NendoU monomer from SARS-CoV-2. From [Kim et al., 2020](#).

Considering the importance of nsp15 for viral evasion from the immune system, we analyzed the druggability of the catalytic site of nsp15 using the SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 crystal structure (PDB: 6wlc). We assessed the amino acid variability of this site across members of Alphacoronavirus and Betacoronavirus genera.

Methods and Results:

Step 1: Assessing the druggability of SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 catalytic site (PDB: 6wlc) with SiteMap

Using SiteMap (Schrodinger, NY) we assessed the druggability of the catalytic site using the druggability score (Dscore). The uridine-binding site of nsp15 has a Dscore of 0.573. This indicates that this site is likely not a druggable site. ([Halgren TA. 2009](#))

Figure 2. Druggability analysis of SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 catalytic site. (PDB: 6wlc)

Step 2. Determining the residues that line nsp15 catalytic site

Using ICM PocketFinder and the nsp15 structure (PDB: 6zsl), we identified 14 amino acid sidechains lining its catalytic site shown in figure 3: H235, Q245, G247, G248, H250, K290, V292, C293, S294, T341, Y343, P344, K345, L346.

Figure 3. The nsp15 catalytic site has 14 surrounding sidechains. (PDB:6wlc) The pocket is occupied by uridine 5'-monophosphate.

Step 3. Make diversity dendrograms for sequences of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera entries from UniProt database.

We surveyed viral proteins from Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. By integrating variability and druggability data, we can then infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum viral inhibitors. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses from circulating viral strains in bat reservoir species.

We looked at twenty-seven reviewed nsp15 sequences from Uniprot entries, where six belong to Alphacoronavirus genus, and twenty-one belong to the Betacoronavirus genus. We then assessed the variability of amino acid lining the nsp15 catalytic site by performing multiple sequence alignment.

We made a diversity dendrogram focusing on the 14 sidechains of nsp15 catalytic site (figure 4) In the dendrogram, the consensus profile at each of the sidechains is shown. The colored letters of varying sizes reflect the residues' profile at each amino acid position of interest. The bigger-sized letter is a more commonly found residue at each position.

At this site, 8 out of 14 residues are identical which translates to 57% sequence identity and 78% sequence conservation.

Step 5: Assessing the genetic variability of nsp15 catalytic site among SARS-CoV-2 samples.

Nicola De Maio, our collaborator from Nick Goldman's lab at the European Bioinformatics Institute, looked at more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients and identified all mutations at nsp15 catalytic site. He identified 7 non-synonymous variants at this site as shown in table 1 including H235Y, G247C, K290N, V292L, Y343C, P344S, K345Q. For example, at residue number 235, the wild-type sidechain in SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 is histidine. In the SARS-CoV-2 genome sample batch Nicola has looked at, he saw that 15869 samples had histidine at that position while there were 4 samples with tyrosine at this exact position. In table 1, the source of the variants is noted under the description column.

Wild Type Residue	Amino Acid Variants from SARS-CoV-2 samples	Description
H235	Y(4),H(15869)	H->Y mutation found in 4 genomes from Netherlands, Australia, and USA, apparently emerged 3 times independently
Q245	Q(15874)	
G247	C(1),G(15872)	Non-synonymous mutation found in 1 sample from USA, EPI_ISL_425170.
G248	G(15873)	
H250	H(15873)	Synonymous variant from 1 sample from Australia, EPI_ISL_417030.
K290	K(15863),N(1)	Non-synonymous variant from 1 sample from Australia, EPI_ISL_430483.
V292	L(1),V(15869)	Non-synonymous variant from 1 sample from Canada, EPI_ISL_418850.
C293	C(15868)	
S294	S(15870)	
T341	T(15874)	
Y343	Y(15872),C(2)	Synonymous variant (codon TAT) seen in 1 sample from USA, EPI_ISL_424241. Non-synonymous variant (codon TGC and aminoacid C) found in 2 samples from USA (WI), apparently a single mutation event.
P344	P(15871),S(3)	S variant found in 3 samples from the Netherlands, apparently from a single mutation event.
K345	Q(1),K(15873)	Q variant found in 1 sample from USA (WI), EPI_ISL_436613.
L346	L(15874)	

Table 1. Amino acid variants observed at the catalytic site of nsp15 across over 15000 SARS-CoV-2 genome samples from COVID-19 patients.

We mapped the sidechain positions of SARS-CoV-2 variants onto SARS-CoV-2 nsp15 crystal structure as shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. Mapping the non-synonymous variants found in SARS-CoV-2 samples onto nsp15 crystal structure. (PDB: 6wlc). The non-synonymous variants (H235, G247, K290, V292, Y343, P344, K345) are shown in orange in sticks representation on the right panel.

Conclusion:

The catalytic site of nsp15, occupied by uridine-5'-monophosphate, is shallow and is predicted to be undruggable. Six key nsp15 catalytic site residues remain conserved in SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2 and MERS-CoV: His235, His250, Lys290, Thr341, Tyr343, and Ser294. ([Kim et al., 2020](#)) Beyond these three viral species, the catalytic site of nsp15 has 57% sequence identity across several entries of the Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera and has 78% amino acid conservation. Despite some evidence highlighting nsp15's role in coronavirus evasion from the host immune response the nsp15 catalytic pocket's shallowness and relatively low sequence identity discourage targeting this site using a broad-spectrum anti-coronavirus small-molecule drug. Despite some evidence highlighting nsp15's role in coronavirus evasion from the host immune response ([Deng et al., 2017](#)), the nsp15 catalytic pocket's shallowness and relatively low sequence identity discourage targeting this site using a broad-spectrum anti-coronavirus small-molecule drug.